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DIRECT/INDIRECT OBJECT WORD ORDER:
A CROSS-LINGUISTIC ANALYSIS*

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ABSTRACT

Osgood has made the claim that because the verb and the direct object are processed semantically as one part of a tripartite cognition in bitransitive sentences, the preferred word order for languages of the world will be one in which the direct object is syntactically adjacent to the verb. Because all bitransitive sentences of the par excellence type already contain semantic features which indicate the categories direct and indirect object, morphological markers of these categories are equally present in both fixed and variable order languages. Information on the phonological marking of syntactic boundaries is insufficient to argue for or against Osgood's hypothesis. In MANDARIN and AMERICAN INDIAN languages, the participation of direct objects in verbal compound constructions in the former and the incorporation of direct objects in the verb stems in the latter, supports Osgood's contention of a strong bond between direct object and verb. In serial verb languages, evolution of a form of the verb 'give' to a calcified indirect object marker supports the hypothesis.

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1.0. Introduction

Surface syntactic ordering of direct objects, indirect objects, and the verb may be examined from a variety of perspectives. Charles Osgood of the University of Illinois has made the following claim: because the verb and direct object are processed semantically as one part of a tripartite cognition in bitransitive sentences, the preferred word order for languages of the world will be one in which the direct object is syntactically adjacent to the verb.

Osgood claims that experimental evidence can be adduced for considering the direct object of bitransitive sentences as cognitively part of the verb. These sentences are of the form,

(1) 'X gave the Y to Z'

where X and Z are usually persons and Y an object. In Osgood (1971), a broad theory of "cognizing and sentencing" has been proposed. Osgood states that the verbalized forms cognizing and sentencing are to be preferred over their noun forms, cognition and sentence, because, psycholinguistically, these are processes rather than states or entities (Osgood, to appear, p. 629). "Cognizing is the process of assigning semantic features to a novel perceptual entity in the 'Subjective Lexicon'" (1971, p. 9). Sentencing, on the other hand, is the process of mapping these semantic features onto the surface structure of language.

The claims of this theory most relevant to the bitransitive clause question are outlined in Osgood's 'Cognitive and sentential complexity' (n.d.). The following several paragraphs are a close paraphrase of this work.

The structures of cognition present in the mind interpret both sentences received and sentences produced. These structures are essentially semantic and are established in pre-linguistic experience with perceived entities and their interaction in perceived events (Osgood, 1971). By "essentially semantic", Osgood refers to the fact that cognitive representations of perceptual (and later, linguistic) signs are simultaneous sets of semantic features, or "code strips". The perceptual and linguistic signs elicit semantic features from the "subjective lexicon" possessed by the individual speaker. Each "code strip" consists of a set of semantic features with non-arbitrary polarity--one pole cognitively positive, one pole cognitively negative (Osgood and Richards, 1973). Such sets of features can be related to the sets of contrasts which Osgood used for his early work with the "semantic differential technique" (Osgood, Suci and Tannenbaum, 1957).

A perceived event is represented in a kind of short-term memory as a simple cognition of tri-partite form. The three components of a simple

cognition are the complete semantic representations ("code strips") of a pair of entities (M_1 and M_2) and the directed action or stative relation ($\rightarrow$) between them. Osgood suggests that Greenberg's article of 1963, 'Some universals of grammar with particular reference to the order of meaningful elements', contains evidence which supports this tripartite analysis.

Directed action relations are coded for "source of action" ($M_1 \rightarrow$) and "recipient of action" ($\rightarrow M_2$). Sentences containing both direct and indirect objects are one kind of directed action relation. Osgood proposes that the subject of the sentences functions as the M_1 component, the indirect object as the M_2 component and the verb and direct object as the $\rightarrow$ (directed action) component of the tripartite event.

Between any one and any other of the tripartite components of the event, the sequence of entering information into and extracting information from the three components in the "operator" (short term memory) corresponds to that sequence which most frequently occurs in the pre-linguistic perception of events, that is, $M_1, \rightarrow, M_2$. Osgood claims (1971, p. 2) that this sequence is the same one as that indicated for perceptual strategies in young children in Bever, 1970¹.

Osgood (1971, p. 2) further claims that complex cognitions are analysable into a concatenation of simple cognitions stored in parallel in the three components of the operator (short term memory). When fused, the concatenation of simple cognitions is semantically equivalent to the complex cognition. The process of analysis of complexes into their simplexes may be regarded as cognizing, and the synthesis of simplexes into complexes to create events may be regarded as sentencing.

In terms of the foregoing summary, the "X" of (1) would function as Osgood's "entity M_1 ", "Z" of (1) "entity M_2 " and "gave the Y" (verb and direct object inclusively) of (1) would function as Osgood's " $\rightarrow$ ", which refers to a "directed action". Osgood has proposed a hypothesis about the ordering of the basic grammatical constituents of the bitransitive sentence. Osgood proposes that these sentences, like others, can be analysed as cognitions with a tripartite form. The bitransitive sentence is a "directed action" in which one person transfers an "object" to another person.

¹The existence of perceived entities and their interaction in perceived events in simple cognitions of tri-partite form should then be demonstrable in the holophrastic, two-word and three-word stages of the acquisition of communicative competence. Their existence in the child's cognitive system in a pre-linguistic stage would of course be somewhat difficult to demonstrate empirically.

This "directed action" may have a number of different surface realizations either within the grammar of one language or across languages. Included in the underlying logical representation of this "directed action" must be a verb of transfer, and three arguments which function as giver, receiver and transferred object. The cognitive representation of such sentences is $M_1 \text{ --- } (M) \text{ ---} \rightarrow M_2$, a simple cognition in Osgood's terms. The giver is the M_1 , the receiver M_2 . The verb of transfer and the transferred object are assimilated in the relation (--- (M) --- >) between M_1 and M_2 . Sentence (1) would be analysed as

(2) 'X (gave the Y to) Z'
 $M_1 \text{ --- } (M) \text{ ---} \rightarrow M_2$

In Osgood's terms, cognitions of verb and direct object are "fused", to form the complex cognition, $\rightarrow$. "Fusion" refers to the joint processing of two cognitive constituents at a semantic level. At this level, the sequence of entering information into and extracting information from the operator (short term memory) for the verb and direct object ($\rightarrow$) would be either verb + direct object or direct object + verb. If these constituents are adjacent and processed as one cognitive constituent at a semantic level, then mapping these structures from a semantic level to a surface syntactic level would require fewer steps (transformations, operations) in languages where they are syntactically adjacent than in languages where they are not. It is thus claimed that the number of languages where these constituents are syntactically adjacent should be greater than the number of languages where these constituents are not syntactically adjacent.

In addition to the cross-language evidence bearing on the Osgood hypothesis to be presented in this paper, there is also evidence on sentence processing in the laboratory reported by Tanz (1973, p. 2). Tanz reports on two experiments of sentence processing. The first experiment which she discusses is designed to discover evidence demonstrating that the O (direct object) is more strongly bonded to the verb than the indirect object. A second experiment would investigate possibly related phenomena in other kinds of "three-entity" sentences. The same dependent variables would be measured in both experiments.

One experiment of the first category would test chunking in cued recall of bitransitive sentences. The grammatical subjects of these sentences would then be presented to the Ss as cues for recall. Ss would be asked to reproduce the remainder of the sentence. Items constituting a cognitive unit should be either recalled or forgotten together. If the Osgood hypothesis on the cognitive structuring of bitransitive sentences holds, the predicted outcome would be that the conditional probability of correct recall of the direct object should be higher than the conditional

probability of recall of the indirect object, given recall of the verb.

Another experiment of the first category would test item recognition time in bitransitive sentences. Ss in this experiment would also be presented with bitransitive sentences. This time, however, they would be shown a probe word after a short interval following presentation of a sentence and asked to indicate if the probe word had been heard in the sentence by answering yes or no. Probe words would be Vs, Ds or Os. The latencies for recognition of direct and indirect object would be measured. Osgood proposes that O recognition will take longer than D recognition because extra time would be necessary to differentiate O features from the V + O (--- (M) --- >) set. This experiment would capture temporal reflections of D and O processing while the first experiment would not.

Following the logic of this position cross-linguistically, one would expect that one might be able to observe that sentences would be preferentially ordered with the direct object appearing contiguous with the verb, and the indirect object appearing at a greater distance from the verb in the surface structure of most languages. An analysis of Blansitt's paper on bitransitive clauses (1973) will show that surface evidence for the Osgood hypothesis is mixed, with approximately equal numbers of languages in the 90+ sample demonstrating indirect and direct object contiguity with the verb. Having seen this, then, one is tempted to examine other aspects of the problem, in the hope that other perspectives may help to shed some light on it.

We pursued various strategies in the analysis of the Osgood hypothesis. Some of these helped to elucidate the problem, while others were rejected because of lack of coverage in the sources, or because they appeared to be unpromising directions for research. Cross-linguistically, there are a number of approaches which might be taken to test the hypothesis. The following approaches will be discussed. First, the Osgood hypothesis will be tested by examining surface syntactic ordering. Second, the phonological marking of syntactic boundaries between the elements of the bitransitive clause may offer information on the "strength" of the bond between grammatical formatives. Third, in those agglutinating languages where nouns are incorporated into the verb stem, the kinds of nouns which are incorporated might offer evidence for or against the Osgood hypothesis. Fourth, the surface structure of co-verbs and serial verbs may offer evidence on Osgood's hypothesis.

For each of these four types of evidence, the following results will be considered confirmatory. For surface syntactic ordering, the presence of a greater number of languages with O contiguous to the verb will tend to

support the hypothesis. Blansitt's work indicates a mixed result. As for phonological evidence, a stronger bond between V + O than between D + O will be considered confirmation of the hypothesis. The incorporation of the direct rather than the indirect object in agglutinating languages will tend to support the hypothesis and finally, zero expression of a pronominal O and proximity of the O to the co-verb in the cases of serial verbs and co-verbs respectively will be considered as confirmation of the Osgood hypothesis.

2.0. Semantic characterization of bitransitivity

Establishing measures of commensurability is one of the initial problems of undertaking a systematic cross-linguistic comparison of a grammatico-semantic category. As Blansitt notes,

"There does not appear to be any way to identify corresponding clause types across language boundaries except through the semantic [emphasis PAS] characterization of a prototype clause or of a specific set of basic clauses; once the structure or structures of the prototype clause or set of basic clauses are identified, other clauses having the same structure will be formally identified as member of the same grammatical type [emphasis PAS]." (1973, p.1)

The domain of analysis in this paper is the set of clauses which are semantically bitransitive irrespective of their surface syntactic form. Those clauses which have syntactic structures such as case-markers, prepositions, etc. identical to the syntactic structures of the bitransitive clause but which are not semantically bitransitive will be excluded from consideration.

In his discussion of the identification of dative case categories (Fillmore's (1965) "to-related indirect object") in his 'Grammatical categories in data collection', Ferguson (1970, p. F5) suggests that it is just as likely that one would expect to find different surface manifestations of the same underlying indirect object relationship in the same language as across languages.

"The analyst is of course prepared to find differences in construction with different verbs within a language and across languages so that there will not be full agreement as to which verbs take indirect objects, what kinds of nouns can serve as indirect objects, and so on..."

Syntactic "sames" may be the surface expression of underlying semantic "differents".

In terms of semantic features there is one type of bitransitive clause which is the bitransitive clause par excellence, which is statistically most

frequent (frequency being one of the characteristics of the unmarked category). In this clause type, the subject is <+human>, the direct object is <-animate>, and the indirect object is <+human>, as in 'The boy gives the book to the man.' In the sources, examples of this type are most common. Bitransitive clauses of other types are permitted. The direct object may be <+human>; the indirect object <+human>, but not <-animate> as in *'The boy gives the man to the book.'

3.0. Surface syntactic ordering and morphological marking

Osgood's hypothesis on the preferred order of direct and indirect objects is concerned with but one of the devices in surface syntax used to indicate the direct-indirect object categories present in the sentence. While word order may facilitate sentence interpretation by indicating direct and indirect objects, morphological devices, such as case endings, may also fulfill this function. Morphological devices may either create redundancy by adding case endings to direct and indirect objects, in languages with a fixed direct-indirect object word order, for example, "overmarking" those categories, or they may obviate the need for word order as a marker of direct-indirect object categories in languages with variable word order. This would explain why a study of word order alone, such as Blansitt 1973, shows the number of languages with direct object in verb-adjacent order as equal to those with indirect object adjacent to the verb.

Our sample of languages includes only examples with nouns in direct and indirect object position. Pronouns have been excluded, not for any theoretical reason, but because of weakness of coverage in the sources. Approximately two thirds of the sources failed to include examples of sentences using only pronominal or pronominal and nominal forms in direct or indirect object position. In many languages, pronominal forms are ordered or affixed in quite different ways from nominal forms. AMERICAN ENGLISH is but one example: 'I gave John the book.' but not *'I gave him it.' It is clear, therefore, that this discussion must then be qualified to present generalizations only about nominal direct and indirect objects.

The languages surveyed are of two basic types: those in which there is a fixed bitransitive word order (in Appendix: FIXED ORDER LANGUAGES), and those languages in which the bitransitive word order varies (in Appendix: VARIABLE ORDER LANGUAGES). The classification of any language as either fixed order or variable order is arbitrary to the extent that discrete boundaries between these two types do not exist. 'Fixed order' refers to a language where one order predominates to the

relative exclusion of any other. 'Variable order' refers to a language in which no one order predominates. It is probably universal that there is no language with only one order for bitransitive sentences. These typologies should, therefore, be regarded as tendencies, rather than as a strict, non-arbitrary dichotomy.

The presence or absence of morphological markers for various sentence constituents is sometimes correlated with one as opposed to another constituent order. This observation indicated that both fixed and variable order languages should be included in the sample, which consisted of 44 languages, 26 of the fixed order type and 18 of the variable order type. Of the 26 fixed order languages 13 were SVO languages. Of these, 10 were SVDO, (S = subject, V = verb, D = indirect object, O = direct object), 2 SVOD, and 1 SOVD, listed in Table 1 (page 126). Another 11 languages were SOV, divided as follows: 5 SODV, 5 SDOV, and 1 SOVD. There were two representatives of VSO languages: both VSOD. Of the 19 languages with variable direct-indirect object order, 14 were SVO, 3 were SOV, and 2 were VSO.

As discussed above, the bitransitive clause par excellence contains an inanimate direct object and an animate indirect object. It is therefore possible to state that because direct and indirect object are already indicated by semantic features, indication of this relationship either through word order or through morphological marking is redundant. Three levels of indicating direct and indirect objects are therefore possible, at least for sentences of the par excellence type: 1) semantic features (obligatory), 2) morphological marking (optional) and 3) word order (optional). Languages which indicate the direct-indirect object relationship with 1) and 2) (variable order languages) are as common as those which indicate the relationship with 1) 2) and 3) (fixed order languages) because of the presence of semantic features which indicate the relationship in both fixed and variable order languages.

Were it not for the presence of the semantic features of $\langle +human \rangle$ for the indirect object and $\langle -animate \rangle$ for the direct object in all bitransitive clauses, irrespective of order, it could be predicted that morphological marking would play a more important role in indicating this relationship in variable order languages. However, because all sentences of the par excellence type are marked by these semantic features in all languages, it is predicted that there will be an equal number of variable and fixed order languages which use morphological markers to indicate the bitransitive relationship.

TABLE 1. MARKING IN LANGUAGES WITH FIXED ORDER

	Extraverbal		Intraverbal	
	D	O	D	O
SVO -SVDO				
Bimoba	-	-	<u>+</u>	-
Gunbalang	-	-	<u>+</u>	-
Hausa	-	-	-	-
Icelandic	-	-	-	-
Indonesian	-	-		+
Iquito	-	-	-	-
Kamba	-	-	<u>+</u>	<u>+</u>
Mamvu	+	-	-	-
Tswana	-	-	<u>+</u>	<u>+</u>
Xhosa	-	-	<u>+</u>	-
SVO-SVOD				
Bini	-	-	-	-
Russian	+	+	-	-
SVO-SOVD				
Yoruba	+	+	-	-
SOV-SODV				
Chagatay	+	+	-	-
Ijo	<u>+</u>	+	-	-
Kewa	-	-	-	-
Orokaiva	+	-	-	-
Somali	<u>+</u>	-	-	-
SOV-SDOV				
Cheremis	+	+	-	-
Chipewyan	+	-	-	-
Maithili	+	+	-	-
Monumbo	-	-	+	+
Uzbek	+	+	-	-
SOV-SOVD				
Huichol	-	-	+	-
VSO-VSOD				
Tahitian	-	+	-	-
Zapotec	+	-	-	-

TABLE 2. MARKING IN LANGUAGES WITH VARIABLE ORDER

	Extraverbal		Intraverbal	
	D	O	D	O
SVO				
Bahnar	+	-	-	-
Coptic	-	<u>+</u>	-	-
Danish	<u>+</u>	-	-	-
Diola Fogny	-	-	-	-
English	<u>+</u>	-	-	-
French	+	-	-	-
German	+	+	-	-
Grebo	-	-	-	-
Italian	+	-	-	-
Jamaican Creole	<u>+</u>	-	-	-
Lithuanian	+	+	-	-
Swahili	<u>+</u>	-	-	-
Swedish	<u>+</u>	-	-	-
Yiddish	+	+	-	-
SOV				
Kapau	+	-	-	-
Telefol	-	-	+	<u>+</u>
Turkish	+	+	-	-
VSO				
Chinantec	-	-	-	-
Chontal	-	-	-	-

SUMMARY OF TABLES 1 and 2 (+ or +)

	FIXED ORDER (1)				VARIABLE ORDER (2)				
	Extraverb.		Intraverb.		Extraverb.		Intraverb.		
	D	O	D	O	D	O	D	O	
SVO (N=26)	3	2	5	2	(N=14)	11	4	0	0
SOV (N=14)	8	5	2	1	(N=3)	2	1	1	1
VSO (N=4)	1	1	0	0	(N=2)	0	0	0	0

In both tables, D refers to the indirect object and O to the direct object, + to the presence of some form of marking of the direct or indirect object either extraverbally: outside the verbal word boundary, as pre-, postposition, case ending, or calcified serial verb, or intraverbally: within the verbal word boundary, as direct or indirect object affix (prefix, infix, suffix, including concord or cross reference) or an affix which signals a bitransitive relationship; - refers to the absence of such marking and ± to optional marking.

A variety of features have been classified as participating in marking in this discussion. The marked/unmarked concept, from Jakobson (1957) cited in Greenberg (1966, p. 72) is defined as follows

"The general meaning of a marked category states the presence of a certain property A; the general marking of the corresponding unmarked category states nothing about the presence of A and is used chiefly but not exclusively to indicate the absence of A."

For our discussion, "the presence of a certain property A" refers to the presence of any feature listed above in either extraverbal or intraverbal position. The presence of these features indicates a marked category. The absence of these features indicates an unmarked category. "Marked" in terms of "unusual" or "low frequency", will be excluded from the definition of these categories.

Excluding word order from the discussion, we see that there are four logically possible ways to mark direct (O) and indirect object (D) relationships. Both may be marked. Neither may be marked. D may be marked and O unmarked. O may be marked and D unmarked. This may be summarized as follows:

	D	O
1.	+	+
2.	-	-
3.	+	-
4.	-	+

From this it follows that the direct object is differentiated from the indirect object in cases 1 (where the marker for D ≠ the marker for O), 3, and 4. Only in case 2 are they not differentiated. If D and O are differentiated within the direct-indirect object relationship, then the relationship will be considered marked. If D and O are not differentiated, the relationship will be considered unmarked.

The direct-indirect object relationship will therefore be considered marked under the following condition: if a language of Tables I and II is followed by one or more +'s. The relationship will be considered unmarked

only if a language is followed by all '-s'. The relationship will be considered optionally marked if one or more '+'s appears and no '+'s appear. Thus, RUSSIAN and CHAGATAY (Table 1) are marked, HAUSA and ICELANDIC are unmarked, and BIMOBA and GUNBALANG are optionally marked. INDONESIAN forms an exception to the conditions stated above, since the kind of marking within the verb merely signals the fact that the verb is bitransitive and does not specify which of the elements outside of the verbal word boundary is the direct and which is the indirect object. In BANTU languages, verb-internal marking often signals the direct/indirect object relationship outside the verb as well, because of the presence of noun class "object prefixes" within the verb, which are in concord with nouns outside the verb. Direct and indirect objects are usually of different noun classes and both employ different "object prefixes" within the verb.

The table below summarizes the results of a compilation of direct-indirect object marking.

TABLE 3.

	Fixed order languages	Variable order languages
Marked	13 (50%)	9 (50%)
Unmarked	6 (23%)	4 (22%)
Optionally marked	7 (27%)	6 (28%)
Total	26 (100%)	18 (100%)

Within the set of languages with a fixed order, MAMVU, RUSSIAN, YORUBA, CHAGATAY, OROKAIVA, CHEREMIS, CHIPEWYAN, MAITHILI, MONUMBO, UZBEK, HUICHOL, TAHITIAN and ZAPOTEC are marked with respect to the direct-indirect object relationship. HAUSA, ICELANDIC, INDONESIAN (which is marked only for bitransitivity; direct and indirect objects are not distinguished by cross-reference), IQUITO, BINI, and KEWA are unmarked. BIMOBA, GUNBALANG, KAMBA, TSWANA, XHOSA, IJO and SOMALI are optionally marked. Within the set of variable order languages, BAHNAR, FRENCH, GERMAN, ITALIAN, LITHUANIAN, YIDDISH, KAPAU, TELEFOL and TURKISH are marked. DIOLA FOGNY, ENGLISH, GREBO, Quiotepec CHINANTEC, JAMAICAN CREOLE, SWAHILI, SWEDISH are optionally marked.

This sample of languages confirms the hypothesis that fixed order languages and variable order languages are equally likely to use morphological marking as an indication of the direct-indirect object relationship. A corollary hypothesis was also stated, although not tested. This corollary hypothesis was that the equal likelihood of morphological marking in fixed and variable order languages is due to the presence of semantic

features in either order, which obviates the necessity of marking this relationship overtly through morphological devices or word order.

These results reveal patterns only at the level of sentencing and are, therefore, not counter-evidence for a hypothesis which would predicate adjacency of verb and direct object at the level of cognizing.

As to the marking of the components (D and O) or the direct-indirect object relationship, D is clearly the marked category. This holds true both for fixed order languages and variable order languages. The results of the chart which follows were arrived at in accord with the following restrictions: if D marking is present either obligatorily (+ in Tables 1 and 2) or optionally ($\pm$ in Tables 1 and 2) and both O's are unmarked (-), then the language is considered to be marked for D. It is also marked for D if D is + and O is $\pm$ either extraverbally or intraverbally. If O marking is present either obligatorily or optionally and both D's are unmarked, then the language is considered to be marked for O. It is also marked for O if O is + and D is $\pm$ either extraverbally or intraverbally. It is marked for both if both D and O agree as + or $\pm$. It is marked for neither if both D and O are - both extraverbally as well as intraverbally.

TABLE 4.	Fixed order languages	Variable order languages	Total
D	9 (39%)	10 (53%)	19 (42%)
O	2 (8%)	1 (5%)	3 (7%)
Both	9 (39%)	4 (41%)	13 (29%)
Neither	6 (14%)	4 (21%)	10 (22%)
Total	26 (100%)	19 (100%)	45 (100%)

Although D is clearly the marked category according to our sample of languages, it is not obvious that there is a significant difference in D marking patterns across fixed order languages as opposed to variable order languages, even though D appears to be marked more often (in half the cases) in variable order languages.

The following languages of the fixed order type are marked for D: BIMOBA, GUNBALANG, MAMVU, OROKAIVA, SOMALI, XHOSA, CHIPEWYAN, HUICHOL, and ZAPOTEC; for O: IJO and TAHITIAN; for both: KAMBA, TSWANA, RUSSIAN, YORUBA, CHAGATAY, CHEREMIS, MAITHILI, MONUMBO and UZBEK; for neither: HAUSA, ICELANDIC, INDONESIAN, IQUITO, BINI and KEWA. The following languages of the variable order type are marked for D: BAHNAR, DANISH, ENGLISH, FRENCH, ITALIAN, JAMAICAN CREOLE, SWAHILI, SWEDISH, KAPAU and TELEFOL; for O: COPTIC; for both: GERMAN, LITHUANIAN, YIDDISH and TURKISH; for neither: DIOLA FOGNY,

GREBO, Quiotepec CHINANTEC and Oaxaca CHONTAL.

At this point, it may be fruitful to examine the question of marking and its relationship to word order. Our sample agrees on the whole with that of Blansitt (1973) regarding marking in variable order languages, but marking in fixed order languages should be analyzed. In variable order languages, it is commonly the case that when a dative or indirect object marker is introduced into the sentence, a shift in word order occurs. This shift is referred to as Dative Movement or Indirect Object Transposition. The indirect object is moved away from the verb, leaving the direct object contiguous to the verb, as in the sample sentences of the appendix: DANISH (98), ENGLISH, JAMAICAN CREOLE (118), SWAHILI (122) or SWEDISH (127), where unmarked D is verb-proximate and marked D is verb-distal.

Returning to Table 3, we see that if the data is rearranged according to D proximity to the verb, O proximity to the verb, and DO neutrality (where they are both adjacent, as ...DVO... or ...OVD...) a different picture emerges, summarized in Table 5, which applies only to fixed order languages.

TABLE 5. FIXED ORDER LANGUAGES

	D proximate	O proximate	Neutral
Marked	4 (27%)	8 (89%)	2 (100%)
Unmarked	5 (33%)	1 (11%)	0
Optionally marked	6 (40%)	0	0
Total	15 (100%)	9 (100%)	2 (100%)

Conclusions based on a limited sample of languages will have to be considered tentative. However on the basis of this sample, it appears that O proximate languages carry significantly greater marking of the direct-indirect object relationship, and are hence less 'natural' than D proximate languages.

However, more central to the discussion is the question of which element is marked when a language is D proximate or O proximate. When the language data are broken down in this fashion, we see that D is marked in 6 cases in D proximate languages while it is marked in only 2 cases in O proximate languages, as in the following table of fixed order languages.

TABLE 6. FIXED ORDER LANGUAGES

	D proximate	O proximate	Neutral
D marked	6 (40%)	2 (22%)	1 (50%)
O marked	1 (7%)	1 (11%)	0
Both marked	3 (20%)	5 (56%)	1 (50%)
Neither marked	5 (33%)	1 (11%)	0
Total	15 (100%)	9 (100%)	2 (100%)

Among fixed order languages, the number of D proximate languages (15) is greater than the number of O proximate languages (9). If the preferred, "natural" word order across languages is one in which the direct object is closer to the verb than the indirect object, as Osgood proposes, then it would be predicted that, in languages in which the non-preferred, "unnatural" word order occurs, the indirect object would be more likely to be morphologically marked than the direct object. This is, in fact, the case. There are six D marked, D proximate languages and only two D marked, O proximate languages.

A discussion of the individual languages and the marking devices employed may be of some assistance in clarifying the above results. Languages which do not indicate the direct-indirect object relationship by pre- or postposition, case ending, object infix, etc. of the direct-indirect object relationship and which indicate it only semantically or by word order will not be covered here.

Of the D proximate languages which mark the direct-indirect object relationship, MAMVU (SVDO) treats the indirect object in one of three ways outlined below (the first and third of these are illustrated in the sample sentence of the appendix (59, 60)). According to Vorbichler (p. 321), the first two devices may alternate freely with one another, while the third is emphatic. Only the indirect object may be marked. The indirect object may be marked first by suffixation of the noun for 'hand' to the noun indirect object (59), second, by the 'normal' indirect object suffix, and third, by the suffixation of 'hand' as well as the indirect object suffix. (60).

CHAGATAY (SODV) marks the direct object by an accusative case ending (contrastive morphologically with the nominative case) and the indirect object by a dative case ending.

In IJO (SODV), the direct object is marked either by a form of the verb 'take' (68), by this form plus a direct object marker, or by the direct object marker alone (69). In IJO the direct object may be marked either by a serial verb, by a serial verb plus indirect object marker, or by the indirect object marker alone. The indirect object is always marked by the serial verb 'give'.

Treatment of languages with serial verbs presented several difficulties. In some of these languages, serial verbs have developed into case markers or prepositions which no longer function as verbs, while in other languages, serial verbs may fulfill the dual function of verb and object marker. However, since both types of language share the function of serial verb as direct or indirect object marker, they will be assigned to languages which utilize marking in addition to word order.

OROKAIVA (SODV) (71) marks the indirect object by a post-position. The direct object is unmarked.

In the second group of D proximate languages, marking of the direct-indirect object relationship is optional. All of these are SVDO, except SOMALI, which is SODV. In BIMOBA, all sentences in which the direct and indirect objects are nouns have a fixed order, even if the indirect object is a pronoun. However, if the direct object is pronominalized, it precedes the indirect object noun. In (48) the indirect object is optionally marked. If the indirect object NP is deleted, the object pronoun suffix becomes obligatory. The same holds true for the deleted and pronominalized direct object, as in (49). The direct object NP has been deleted and the object suffix becomes obligatory.

In GUNBALANG, marking of the indirect object is optional, although the example sentence cited includes it. The indirect object is marked by an affix which appears in the verb stem and is followed by the affix -marnayn-. The object marker (cf. (50)) refers to the direct object only in untransitive clauses. In bitransitive clauses, it may refer only to the indirect object.

In KAMBA, there is no verb-external marking of the direct and indirect object relationship other than word order. Internally, the verb optionally contains either a direct or an indirect object prefix. When direct and indirect object prefixes are present in the verb, it is not stated which is nearer to the verb stem. However, in bitransitive sentences, the indirect object prefix is most frequent in occurrence, as in (58). Use of the direct object prefix tends to "definitize" the direct object.

Like BIMOBA, GUNBALANG, and KAMBA, TSWANA is SVDO. In this language, though "...both objects may be either alternatively or simultaneously represented by their object concords [as in KAMBA; PAS], it is more usual for the principal object [indirect object: PAS] to be so treated. When both objects are expressed or represented by their object concords, the principal object, or its concord, has precedence of order and is placed nearest the verb stem." (Cole, 1955, p. 430) (61) is the only sentence which Cole cites which is close to a basic bitransitive clause.

XHOSA (SVDO), which also utilizes verb internal marking of the direct-indirect object relationship, permits only the indirect object prefix within the verb, but its presence is optional. The sample sentence (62) includes the indirect object prefix.

In SOMALI (SODV), marking depends on the alternants of the verb 'give'. In (72), the postposition 'to' is obligatory following the indirect object. In (73) the notion of bitransitivity is inherent in the verb 'give to' and is not expressed syntactically. The word order with both verbs is identical.

In RUSSIAN (SVOD), CHEREMIS, MAITHILI, and UZBEK (SDOV), the marking of the relationship is by case ending. In all of these languages, the direct object is adjacent to the verb. In RUSSIAN, as in (64), accusative then dative follows the verb in the normal order, according to Pulkina (p. 88). Informants emphasize the fact that although this is the normal order, if the dative element is stressed, then the indirect object NP may precede a direct object NP. In UZBEK, (79) exemplifies normal word order. When the direct object is a pronoun, it precedes the indirect object, whether the indirect object is a noun or a pronoun, as in (80).

According to Li (p. 422) the normal mechanism for marking subsidiary objects in CHIPEWYAN (SDOV) is by the addition of a postposition. Pronominal objects may appear inside the verb (p. 410). Li's examples only pertain to direct objects (p. 416), benefactive, reflexive, etc. and he does not discuss whether indirect object pronominals may be included in this list.

MONUMBO (SDOV) is marked only verb internally, where it contains object affixes which refer to direct and indirect NPs outside the verb.

In Tryon's discussion of TAHITIAN (p. 29), it is suggested that proper and common nouns are marked when in direct object position, but there is no discussion of nouns in indirect object position. Pronouns in the indirect object position take the form of "Pronoun Object" (p. 31-32) as in (84).

According to Briggs (p. 92), the indirect object in ZAPOTEC is marked by a particle phrase, as in (85), and it follows the direct object (VSOD).

Other approaches to the question of direct and indirect object were also considered in the initial stages of examination of the hypothesis.

4.0. Phonological marking of syntactic boundaries

There is evidence for the Osgood O proximity hypothesis in the phonological marking which occurs across syntactic categories in variable order languages. In the present case (FRENCH), only liaison is considered, although a wider treatment of phonological marking across

word boundaries, tone shifts, etc. For FRENCH, the presence of liaison between the verb and the direct object but not between the verb and the indirect object will confirm the hypothesis (Case 1 in Table 7 below). The presence of liaison between the verb and the indirect object but not between the verb and the direct object will deny the hypothesis (Case 2 below). The presence of liaison in both cases or its absence in both cases will neither confirm nor deny the hypothesis (Cases 3 and 4).

		1	2	3	4
Verb and	O	+	-	+	-
	D	-	+	+	-

While this table refers primarily to liaison in FRENCH, it may also be used as a general typology of phonological marking across the syntactic categories of verb, direct and indirect object.

Selkirk's work (1972) on liaison between verb and indirect object and verb and direct object indicate that for FRENCH, phonological liaison occurs both with D and O adjacent to the verb in normal declarative order, as in the following sentences

(3) Nous donnerons[^] une somme à l'organisation.

(4) Nous donnerons[^] à l'organisation une somme.

where [^] = phonological liaison. If the direct object is removed by a transformation, liaison is blocked, as follows

(5) La somme que nous donnerons/ à l'organisation est grande.

where / = blocking of phonological liaison. Selkirk implies that liaison would be blocked in the case of indirect object as well. This evidence, therefore, neither confirms nor denies the Osgood hypothesis.

In addition to Selkirk, little work had been done on phonological marking of syntactic categories. Although this may prove to be a promising area for future work, there is presently insufficient material for a large cross-language sample.

5.0. Noun incorporation

Further evidence supporting the thesis that O tends to act as part of the verb while D may in fact, act cognitively as the receiver of the action may be found in the morphology of many AMERICAN INDIAN languages. Alfred Kroeber and Edward Sapir were early observers of this. If direct objects are incorporated into the verb stem with greater fre-

quency than indirect objects, this will be considered as supporting evidence for the Osgood hypothesis. If the opposite occurs, this will be considered as evidence denying the Osgood hypothesis.

In an article concerned mainly with the subject of noun incorporation² in the verb stem, Sapir suggests that pronoun incorporation in the verb also occurs:

"A very large number of American, as of non-American, languages make use in the verb of affixed elements of pronominal signification; they are, as regards their syntactical use, very commonly subjective, less frequently, though by no means rarely, also objective, and still less commonly they indicate also dative, ablative, or other case relations." (Sapir, 1911, p. 250)

This statement indicates that the direct object is more likely to be incorporated in the verb stem than the indirect object. Incorporation of direct object nouns in verbs occurs while incorporation of indirect object nouns does not.³ This supports Osgood's hypothesis that Os are

²It may be noted that one of the chief motivations for Sapir's publication of this article was to rebut Kroeber, by demonstrating that not only direct objects but also other case-indicating morphs appeared in the same slot in the verb paradigm. Morphological "sames" may have represented semantic "different." The fact that Kroeber laid so much stress on direct object incorporation is intuitive evidence of direct object as incorporated object par excellence.

³Edith Moravcsik suggests (personal communication) that noun incorporation could be extended to include the consideration of English compounds which would show evidence of verb-direct object compounds. However, most English verb compounds are of the instrumental type, such as

- (A) He pistol-whipped the boy.
- (B) He hand-carried (hand-delivered) the message.
- (C) They steam-cleaned the engine.
- (D) They hand-polished the car.
- (E) They spray-painted the garage.
- (F) ? They brush-painted the garage.

English will not permit compounds which would incorporate direct objects such as

- (G) **He book-gave the girl.
- (H) **He ball-hit the boy.

John Rohsenow has suggested (personal communication) several of these examples. Rohsenow also proposes that

- (I) *He girl-gave the book.

is more acceptable (although ungrammatical) than (G).

cognitively part of the verb in "double object" constructions. O pronouns are more often incorporated or affixed to the verb complex. In the languages of the world, it is generally true that pronouns are more often incorporated than nouns. A good example of the difference in word order constraints for nouns and pronouns in bitransitive sentences is ENGLISH:

- | | | | | | |
|------|---------------------------|---|---|----------------|----------------|
| (6) | He gave the book to John. | S | V | O _n | D _n |
| (7) | He gave John the book. | S | V | D _n | O _n |
| (8) | He gave it to him. | S | V | O _p | D _p |
| (9) | *He gave him it. | S | V | D _p | O _p |
| (10) | He gave the book to him. | S | V | O _n | D _p |
| (11) | He gave him the book. | S | V | D _p | O _n |
| (12) | He gave it to John. | S | V | O _p | D _n |
| (13) | *He gave John it. | S | V | D _n | O _p |

In BANTU languages, there seems to be some evidence for D attraction. When D and O are both present, and only one of these can be marked in the verb, D is selected as pronominal affix. Further investigation might clarify the case for AMERICAN INDIAN languages, especially in the UTO-AZTECAN groups which Sapir discusses.

Regarding noun incorporation within verbs, Sapir defines this process as the "compounding [of] a noun stem with a verb..." (p. 257). The compounding principle may therefore include such syntactically diverse formations as instrumental, locative, subjective and objective noun incorporation. There is no mention at all of D noun incorporation. Incorporated direct object nouns are most common in transitive verbs, while incorporated subject nouns generally occur with intransitive verbs. The order of the incorporated noun within the verb varies; it may occur either prefixed or suffixed. IROQUOIS, PAWNEE, SHOSHONEAN and TAKELMA are prefixing; YANA and TSIMSHIAN are suffixing. NAHUATL, a UTO-AZTECAN language of central Mexico, is one of the most commonly cited languages to illustrate noun incorporation, including incorporation of the direct object. In NAHUATL, both pronominal and nominal O incorporation are possible.

- (14) ni-c-qua in nacatl
 "I-it-eat the flesh"

and

- (15) ni-nica-qua
'I-flesh-eat'

in which the -tl nominal suffix is dropped (Sapir, p. 260). Meanings of the two variant sentences have been reported to be contrastive, however; the former pertains to what Sapir refers to as the 'particular', which may be interpreted as 'single occurrence' as well, while he refers to the latter as 'general', which may be interpreted as 'multiple occurrence'. In NAHUATL, object incorporation is but one kind of the more general process of noun incorporation.

In SHOSHONEAN languages object incorporation is quite common, cf. Sapir's example from SOUTHERN PAIUTE:

- (16) gām'ŪyaainUmpUŷa'
'(he) used to hunt jack rabbits'
(gām'U = 'jack rabbit'; yaai = 'to hunt'; -nUm- = usitative;
-pUŷai = remote past)

In both NAHUATL and SOUTHERN PAIUTE, there are a number of resemblances in the manner in which objects are incorporated: the incorporated noun is prefixed to the verb stem, suffixes found in the absolute form of the noun are lacking when it is incorporated. These similarities and others are used by Sapir primarily for the purposes of classification within the UTO-AZTECAN language family (p. 267).

In a language unrelated to NAHUATL and PAIUTE this process can also be observed. YANA, a Central California language, uses incorporation primarily with direct objects, but also with locatives and other formations. Of these, only incorporation of the direct object will be considered.

- (17) k:utxáisndja
'I am thirsty'
(k:ut = 'to want, desire'; -xai- = incorporated form of xána,
hána 'water'; -si- present tense; -ndja = 'I')
- (18) k:unmiyáusindja
'I am hungry'
(-miyau = reduced form of mô'yauna 'eating, food')

In TAKELMA, a language of Southwestern Oregon, there is a syntagmatic contrast between pronominal incorporation and nominal incorporation. Pronouns are suffixed to the verb and nouns are prefixed. Bound pronominal and nominal forms vary in their syntagmatic behavior in TAKELMA and other languages, pronouns and nouns in free form vary in ENGLISH and other languages. Sapir also reports that incorporated

pronouns are more strongly "welded" to the verb than nouns. We interpreted this to mean that there is a greater degree of phonological assimilation with pronouns than with nouns. Again, only noun object examples are given:

- (19) xāp:iⁱ n^o k'wa
'he was warming his back'
(xā- 'back' incorporated with objective meaning, cf. xa-hām-t'k' 'my back'; p:iⁱ 'fire' incorporated with instrumental meaning, cf. p:iy-ā-t'k' 'my fire'; -n^og- aorist stem 'to warm'; -k'wa 'one's own')
- (20) gwenwayasgut:úsgathi
'with (his) knife he cut their necks'
(gwen- 'neck' incorporated with objective meaning, cf. gwen-hau-x-dèk 'my nape'; waya 'knife' incorporated with instrumental meaning, cf. wayàt'k' 'my knife'; 'sgut:usgat-, distributive of sgó^ud- aorist stem 'to cut'; -hi instrumental suffix)

Further examples of this type appear in ONEIDA and PAWNEE. Sapir provides several examples for each language.

Similar to noun incorporation in AMERICAN INDIAN languages is the process of compounding in MANDARIN; Chao defines a compound as "a combination of two or more words bound together to form one word." (p. 359). In his discussion of verb-object compounds, he states that this type of construction must satisfy one of the following conditions to be considered a compound:

1. one or both of the constituents being bound
2. neutral tone in the object
3. exocentricity of the construction as a whole
4. lexicality (specialization) of meaning

Although it would be possible for indirect objects to be incorporated within the compound under one of the above conditions, this does not occur in any of the numerous examples which Chao cites.

If either constituent is bound, the constituent is a compound. Examples of full-bound compounds: cl.ii-hong 'raise disturbance, start something for fun'; daa-shaan 'strike flash, there is lightning'; daa-tih 'strike sneeze, to sneeze'; gaw-juang 'accuse (on a) case, bring suit'. Examples of bound-free compounds: gaw-lao 'announce old age, retire'; gawstyr 'request leave, say formal good-by'; nah-shuey 'enter tax, pay tax'. Examples of bound-bound compounds: buh-jiing 'display scenes, design or set (stage) scenery'; chiuh-shyh 'depart from the world, die'; germing 'remove the (divine) mandate (to rule), overthrow the ruling regime, start a revolution'.

Compounds may also be formed by meeting condition two: since a verb-object phrase must have stress on the object, a verb-object construction must be a compound if the object is in the neutral tone: shiou.shing 'cultivate conduct, become a Buddhist'; der.tzuey 'get offense, offend'.

When a verb-object compound does not function as a whole as an intransitive verb, it is an exocentric compound. All of the above compounds function as intransitive verbs. If the verb-object compound functions as (1) transitive verb, (2) noun, (3) adjective, (4) adverb, or (5) interjection, it is exocentric. Those which function as nouns may in turn act as representatives of agency, instrumentality, action, or goal of the verb (Chao, p. 415-24).

When Chao is unable to label a construction as a verb-object compound on the basis of any of the conditions already stated, but nonetheless intuits a construction as such, he resorts to the final condition, lexicality or specialization of meaning, which he admits, is "not only non-structural in nature, but also more difficult to apply, since it is a factor which admits of differences of degree." (Chao, p. 423). Crucial to the definition of this type seems to be the inseparability of the meaning components of the verb-object construction: "meanings will have to be given as wholes in addition to the meaning of their parts." (p. 423-24).

Although MANDARIN is noted for the richness of formation of various syntactic types of compounds, of which verb-object compounds represent only a part, there is no type in which the D noun may be incorporated into one of these formations.

In the case of pronoun incorporation, which also occurs in AMERICAN INDIAN languages and in other languages of the world as well, especially NIGER-CONGO languages, it is commonly the case that the indirect object is incorporated. We have referred to examples of this type above in discussion of specific languages.

In both MANDARIN and the AMERICAN INDIAN languages discussed here, evidence for support of the Osgood hypothesis is strong. In the former, direct objects are more likely to participate in verbal compound constructions, while in the latter, direct object nouns are more likely to be incorporated in the verb.

A possible explanation for the apparent contradictory evidence that direct object nouns and indirect object pronouns are most likely to appear as bound within the verb is that: 1) the semantic range of direct objects is greater than the semantic range of indirect objects 2) in-

direct objects which appear outside the verb are frequently omitted. It is probably also true (but this is only surmised) that sentences with a nominal direct object and a pronominal indirect object are far more frequent than sentences with nominal direct and indirect objects or sentences with pronominal direct objects and nominal indirect objects.

6.0. Serial verb constructions

6.1. West African languages. In a limited number of the languages of the world, there exists a construction which signals the underlying semantic nature of double complement constructions. This grammatical structure, the serial verb construction, occurs in the NIGER-KORDOFANIAN languages of West Africa, in AKAN and some other KWA languages. In some of these languages, serial verbs have become calcified as "prepositional" markers of direct and indirect objects and other lexical forms. In the remainder of the languages of the world, the origin of direct and indirect object markers is not so transparently indicated. Although serial verbs are used in other constructions in these West African languages as well, such as inchoatives and causatives, those to be discussed in the present context signal direct and indirect objects in dual complement sentences. Briefly, the "dative" serial construction usually takes the form

(21) "take X give Y"

in most of these languages. In this example, "X" is the O, "Y" the D. The direct object in the serial verb construction is usually indicated by some shape of the verb "take". The indirect object is not explicitly marked. Other verbs in serial verb constructions may appear in the position occupied by 'give' in (21) as in

(22) "take X { lend, sell, offer } Y".

This construction may occur in sentences where an O and a D are possible. It may also take the form

(23) "take X { lend, offer, sell } give Y".

The verb preceding the "X" would be glossed as 'take, join with, together with'. The form for "take" is often used as a conjunction between two NPs, but not between two Ss. The fact that the verb form preceding the O is obligatory and the verb form preceding the D is optional lends support to the Osgood hypothesis. Thus, there appears to be a "strong link" between the verb form preceding O and a "weak link" preceding D.

Serial verbs are contained within a single sentence in which a succession of acts is performed by the same person, the subject-actor.

The range of syntactic and semantic phenomena to which this type of construction is related is broad. Inchoatives, instrumental and manner adverbials, datives, benefactives, locatives, causatives, comparatives and auxiliaries are included (Stahlke, 1970, p. 61). An example from YORUBA (Stahlke's (12), p. 63) should make their use clear:

- (24) mo mú ìwé wá fún
"I took book came gave you"
'I brought you a book.'

The underlined elements are verbs.

This sentence can be contrasted with YORUBA:

- (25) mo bá o mú iwé wá
"I for you took book came"
'I brought a book on your behalf.' (Stahlke's (3))

In YORUBA, datives and benefactives have separate forms in the surface structure, while in YATYE, a distantly related language which also makes considerable use of serial verb constructions, the two processes have merged:

- (26) àmì awá ínyahwè ibí akà àwò
"I took book came for you"
'I brought you a book.'
or
'I brought a book on your behalf.' (Stahlke's (14))

Features of serial verb structure may shed light on the universals of the surface and deep structure of O and D. For example, there are two restrictions on double object constructions which occur in TWI, as discussed by Stewart (1963).

In this language the only possible position for an "object pronoun" is immediately after a verb (Stewart, p. 145). By "object pronoun", Stewart refers to the O, as we have discussed in Section 3. Most languages differ in the types of permitted D/O word order, depending upon whether the formatives are nouns or pronouns. Although the sentence

- (27) ɔfemm me ne pɔnk nó
"He-lent me his horse that"
'He lent me his horse.'

is possible,

- (28) *ɔfemm me no
"He-lent me it"

is not.

- (29) ɔfɛmm no me
 'He-lent it me''

does not violate the cooccurrence restrictions, which apply to double pronoun O/D sentences. A serial verb 'take' is necessary to make (28) grammatical, as in

- (30) ɔde no fɛmm me
 'He-take it lent me''
 'He lent it to me.'

Just as the pronoun O only appears after the serial verb de, so is it with the definite direct object with certain verbs.

This restriction applies not only to overt pronouns, pronouns which appear on the surface, but also to the so-called 'zero object pronoun', which is a common occurrence in West African languages. An animate direct object noun is replaced by the inanimate object pronoun. Thus, with an animate O noun, we have

- (31) ɔfɛmm me ne pɔnkɔ́ nó
 'He-lent me his horse that''
 'He lent me his horse.'

and

- (32) ɔde nó fɛmm me
 'He-take it lent me''
 'He lent it to me.'

where the O is pronominalized.

With an inanimate noun, we have

- (33) ɔfɛmm me n'á dwá nó
 'He-lent me this stool that''
 'He lent me his stool.'

and

- ɔde fɛmm me
 'He take (it) lent me''
 'He lent it to me.'

with $\emptyset$ expression of the inanimate pronoun object. (Stewart, p. 149)

The second restriction which Stewart notes for TWI is that "some verbs which are frequently followed by an indefinite direct object are never followed by a definite direct object" (p. 147). Thus,

(34) ɔmaa me siká
"He-gave me money"

and

(35) ɔmaa me siká bí
"He-gave me money some"
'He gave me some money.'

are possible, but

(36) *ɔmaa me siká nó
"He-gave me money the"
'He gave me the money.'

is not possible, because of the presence of the definite particle nó. The order with a definite O must be

(37) ɔde siká nó maa me
"He-take money the gave me"
'He gave me the money.'

using the serial verb de. The only verbs which Stewart lists as belonging to this series are verbs which can take both Os and Ds, such as: ma 'give, give away', kyɛ 'give, give away', brɛ 'bring', and mane 'send'. Only these verbs are restricted as to object-type selection. Others may be included in this series, but they are not mentioned.

A similar restriction also applies in G^ã, a language related to TWI: if the second (<-anim), direct) object is also <-specific), then a sentence like the following is possible:

(38) òtò há è bí lè tso-bí
"Oto gave his child the (a) wood-child"
'Oto gave his child a doll.' (Trutenau, p. 76)

but if the direct object is (-anim, +spec) then it cannot follow the above verb há, even at a distance, but must be "protected" by the presence of the serial verb kè which precedes the "zero pronominalization" of the direct object with no overt expression occurs with serial verbs in a D/O construction in G^ã as in the following examples:

(39) òtò kè tso-bí lè há è bí lè
"Oto took doll the gave his child the"
'Oto gave the doll to his child.' (Trutenau, p. 77)

which appears as follows if the subject, D and O are pronominalized:

- (40) ē kē ∅ hǎ lē
"He took (it) gave (to) it"
'He gave (it) (to) it.'

That zero pronominalization may occur on the surface in many of these languages is evidence of a more "natural", less "marked" nature of the O. The restriction on the selection of definite Os only after some serial verbs as discussed by Stewart (p. 147) and the lack of restrictions on Ds, seems to indicate in these cases a greater tendency toward markedness in the case of indirect objects.

6.2. CHINESE languages. Serial verb constructions in MANDARIN CHINESE present further evidence on the Osgood hypothesis. Li and Thompson, 1973, include the bitransitive verb as a sub-type of the serial verb. Their paper attempts to present pro- and counter-examples for serial verb constructions as either subordinate or coordinate. From their discussion, several semantic types of serial verb constructions are said to occur. Some sentences may indicate actions or events denoted by the predicates which are consecutive. Others result in a purpose reading. Still others may appear to express simultaneity of actions or events, while a final type may express "alternating" actions.

The co-verbs of CHINESE form a closed set, of which one is gei, 'give, for'. This co-verb may be used in sentences such as the following

- (41) Zhang-san gei wo mai yifu
"Zhang-san for me buy clothes" (Li and Thompson, p. 3)

where it does not function as a main verb. It may, however, also function in the capacity of a main verb as in the following sentence

- (42) Wo gei ta tang
'I give him candy.' (Li and Thompson, p. 3)

Sentence (41) looks very much like a serial verb construction. Li and Thompson do not consider the co-verbs to be verbs, but rather prepositions:

Semantically, these co-verbs are not functioning as true verbs in constructions such as (41) [PAS], but as prepositions, introducing phrases which could be labeled with such case names as Benefactive... Syntactically, important characteristics of co-verbs distinguish them from main verbs, such as their inability to take various aspectual particles and to be reduplicated. For these reasons, we consider co-verb sentences to be distinct from serial verb sentences. (p. 4)

Whether these co-verbs are considered as verbs or as prepositions, their syntactic position indicates a closer relationship to the D than to the O in terms of contiguity.

In TAIWANESE⁴, a SOUTHERN MIN language related to MANDARIN and the rest of the CHINESE "dialects", the following sentence type may be considered *primus inter pares*:

- (43) Guo ho i ci
'I give him money.'

or most frequent, "normal" and "grammatically acceptable". The following two versions are also possible:

- (44) Guo ci ho i a
'I money give him (particle)'

and

- (45) Ci: guo ho i a
'Money I give him (particle).'

The latter sentence is a version of (44) in which 'money' has been topicalized. The ho in TAIWANESE as a co-verb (preposition) may not occur when it is also used as the main verb, although it frequently occurs in sentences with other main verbs, where it may never be affiliated with O. The picture in CANTONESE is quite different. The 'double pei construction' in CANTONESE is the preferred form

- (46) ɲɔ pei ts'in (pei) koey
'I give money give him'

As we have indicated, the use of the second pei is optional, although the most frequent sentences using this construction include it. Topicalization may also occur, as in the following sentence

- (47) Ts'in ɲɔ pei koey
'Money I give him.'

in which the topicalized O is fronted. If the D, koey, is topicalized, it cannot be fronted as the O can. Speakers of CANTONESE state that D may be topicalized by the addition of extra stress, in (46) or (47). Without topicalization, in the "normal" form, the first pei is used as a verb, the second possible as preposition. That the D, koey, is sometimes marked by the presence of pei, and the O ts'in is not so marked, seems to argue for the Osgood hypothesis.

In the case of both languages of West Africa and a number of CHINESE "dialects", the following historical development has been observed for

⁴ Thanks are due to Lin Shuang-Fu and Tse Gwo-Ping for their provision of examples from TAIWANESE and CANTONESE respectively.

serial verbs. If a language of this type develops a prepositional marker for the indirect object, this marker is derived from a calcified form of the verb 'give'. The direct object has no such marker. This follows generalization 1, below.

7.0. Conclusions

On the basis of the foregoing areas of evidence it is possible to make the following tentative generalizations about the bitransitive clause par excellence in which the subject is $\langle +\text{human} \rangle$, the indirect object is $\langle +\text{human} \rangle$, and the direct object is $\langle -\text{animate} \rangle$

1. If the direct object is morphologically marked in a sentence then the indirect object is also morphologically marked in the same sentence. (exception: TAHITIAN)
2. 80% of the languages in our sample which indicate the direct or the indirect object by word order also indicate them by morphological marker. Thus, even in those languages with a fixed word order, either the direct object or the indirect object may be indicated by, say, the presence of a preposition, suffix, etc.
3. In two-thirds of the languages sampled the indirect object is marked either extra- or intra-verbally when it is contiguous with the verb in fixed order languages. When the direct object is contiguous with the verb, the indirect object is marked in approximately the same proportion of languages.
4. In variable order SVO languages, where indirect-object marking is optional, the indirect object is contiguous with the verb when it is unmarked, but the direct object is contiguous with the verb when it is marked.

Osgood has made the claim that because the verb and the direct object are processed semantically as one part of a tripartite cognition in bitransitive sentences, the preferred word order for languages of the world will be one in which the direct object is syntactically adjacent to the verb. Ordering of the direct object adjacent to the verb is no more frequent than ordering of the indirect object adjacent to the verb. Because all bitransitive sentences of the par excellence type (D: $\langle +\text{human} \rangle$, O: $\langle -\text{animate} \rangle$) already contain semantic features which indicate the categories direct and indirect object, morphological markers of these categories are equally present in both fixed and variable order languages. Information on the phonological marking of syntactic boundaries is insufficient to argue for or against Osgood's hypothesis. In MANDARIN and AMERICAN INDIAN languages, the participation of direct objects in verbal compound construc-

tions in the former and the incorporation of direct objects in the verb stems in the latter, supports Osgood's contention of a strong bond between direct object and verb. In serial verb languages, evolution of a form of the verb 'give' to a calcified indirect object marker supports the hypothesis.

APPENDIX
SAMPLE SENTENCES
FIXED ORDER LANGUAGES

SVO Languages -- Dominant Order SVDO

BIMOBA

(48) u tur (ɔ) n chamba doorek
he gave (him) my father pig
'He gave (him) my father a pig.' (85)⁵ SVDO

(49) u tur-ɔ n chamba
he gave-it my father
'He gave it to my father.' (85) SVOD

GUNBALANG

(50) Kirrimarrk na-kuji kapurrun kikiwayn ka -putu-marnayn-purrjuwa
man male-one they all he them for tells story
'A man is telling all of them a story.' (33) SVDO

HAUSA

(51) nā ba dōkī dāwā
I gave horse guinea corn
'I gave the horse some guinea corn.' (2) SVDO

ICELANDIC

(52) Gísli gaf honum (Pétri) kveri é
Gisli gave him Petri the booklet.
'Gisli gave him (Petri) the booklet.' (172) SVDO

INDONESIAN

(53) Saja akan membeli buku itu
I am going to buy book that
'I am going to buy that book.' (152)

(54) Saja akan membelikan Siti buku itu
I am going buy for Siti book that
'I am going to buy that book for Siti.' (153) SVDO

(55) Ali mengirim surat
Ali sent letter
'Ali sent a letter.' (153)

(56) Ali mengirimi adiknja surat
Ali sent his younger brother letter
'Ali sent his younger brother a letter.' (153) SVDO

⁵ Refers to page number where sentence appears in source.

IQUITO

- (57) nuu-miitáá yaa siyuuyáána núú
he-is giving fisherman it
'He is giving it to the fisherman.' (158) SVDO

KAMBA

- (58) Níngũmũtavya mũndũ ũũ ũvoo
I-pres. -him-tell man this story
'I am telling this man the story.' (30) SVDO

MAMVU

- (59) masì múdo-elí erí relí
I-gave man-hand thing one
'I gave the man a thing.' (321) SVDO

- (60) eqe-qóqba osì indélf-ni ðfqp
woman-weepy-eyed gave him-hand-ind. obj. amulet
'The weepy eyed woman gave him an amulet.' (325) SVDO

TSWANA

- (61) Mosadi ojesa ngwana dijô
woman feeds child food
'The woman feeds the food to the child.' (431) SVDO

XHOSA

- (62) ufanike umnqweno wentliziyo yabo
he-them-gave desire (of) heart their
'He gave them the desire of their heart.' (165) SVDO

SVO Languages -- Dominant Order SVOD

BINI

- (63) òsè mwen ya èbè èva nè òzo
friend my gave book two to Ozo
'My friend gave two books to Ozo.' (219) SVOD

RUSSIAN

- (64) on dal p'ismó bratu
he gave letter brother-dat.
'He gave a letter to the brother.' (informant) SVOD

SVO Languages -- Dominant Order SOVD

YORUBA

- (65) ó fi mí fún u
he took me gave him
'He gave me to him.' (83) SOVD
- (66) ó fi owó náà fún mi
he took money the gave me
'He gave me the money.' (83)

CHAGATAY

- (67) ol kentni Hācī Begning variqlariga berdi
he village that Hacı Beg's heirs gave
'He gave that town to Hacı Beg's heirs.' (86) SOVD

IJO

- (68) erí, opúru-mo àkí, tọboú pìrì-mì
he crayfish-pl. take boy give-he
'He gave the crayfish to the boy.' (54) SODV
- (69) erí, opúru-mo-nì, tọboú pìrì-mì
he crayfish-pl. -linker boy give-he
'He gave the boy a crayfish.' (54)

KEWA

- (70) né-mé sápi áá-para mená láápo kála-lo
I sweet potato man-and pig two give-I am
'I am giving sweet potato to the man and the pig.' (65) SODV

OROKAIVA

- (71) Na nau eti nau iae embo iki-he-n-a
I my bag my daughter to give-near past-I-indicative
'I gave my bag to my daughter.' (52) SODV

SOMALI

- (72) la'agta 'Ali u diib
money Ali to give
'Give the money to Ali.' (22) (S)ODV
- (73) la'agta 'Ali sii
money Ali give-to
'Give the money to Ali.' (22) (S)ODV

SOV Languages -- Dominant Order SDOV

CHEREMIS

- (74) tudo čort-lan kūrəkəm urgen
 he devil-dat. coat-acc. he-sewed
 'He sewed a coat for the devil.' SDOV

CHIPEWYAN

- (75) setəue sa kún ʔeʔtsi
 my grandson for me fire he made
 'My grandson made a fire for me.' (422) SDOV

MAITHILI

- (76) rāmake pāc^a tā rupaiā nāhi debainhi
 'I will not give Rama five rupees.' (591) (S)DOV

MONUMBO

- (77) kuan ta aluak-tsind-iŋ-et
 a banana bring-you-him-it
 'Bring him a banana.' (9) (S)DOV

- (78) Manúmbiam nu unambo kurúmbe nde:ip aka
 Manumbiam 's wife the children coconuts and

kuande naka kanadúnge upikem
 bananas and taro she gave them those things

'Mamumbiam's wife gave the children coconuts, bananas and taro.'
 (9) SDOV

UZBEK

- (79) men uŋ-ga ɔlma-ni berman
 I him-dat. apple-acc. I'll give
 'I'll give him the apple.' (145) SDOV

- (80) men u-ni se ŋ-ga yub raman
 I it-acc. you-dat. I'll send
 'I'll send it to you.' (146) SOVD

SOV Languages -- Dominant Order SOVD

HUICHOL

- (81) téwí kucíira kaníi+géit ani yu?iwá
 man machete he-gave-him his-brother
 'The man give his brother a machete.' (51) SOVD

DIOLA-FOGNY

- (91) εjamεnεy furiaf nisεnf
goat foof I-gave DO(S)V
- (92) furiaf εjamεnεy nisεnε OD(S)V
- (93) εjamεnεy nisεnε furiaf D(S)VO
- (94) furiaf nisεnε εjamεnεy O(S)VD
- (95) nisεnε fufiaf εjamεnεy (S)VOD
- (96) nisεnε εjamεnεy furiaf
'I gave the food to the goat.' (S)VDO

FRENCH

- (97) La nature...offre au...marcheur des secrets
nature offers to the walker secrets
'Nature offers secrets to the walker.' (73) SVDO
- (98) La nature offre des secrets au marcheur
nature offers secrets to the walker
'Nature offers secrets to the walker.' (informant) SVOD

GERMAN

- (99) Die Bibliothek leiht dem Studenten ein Buch
the library lends the student a book (127) SVDO
- (100) Die Bibliothek leiht ein Buch dem Studenten (informant)
'The library lends a book to the student.' SVOD
- (101) Die Bibliothek leiht es ihm
the library lends it to him (127) SVOD
- (102) Die Bibliothek leiht ihm ein Buch
the library lends him a book (informant) SVDO
- (103) Die Bibliothek leiht es dem Studenten
the library lends it to the student (informant) SVOD

GREBO

- (104) hí nε nɔ
give it him
'Give it to him.' (102) (S)VOD
- (105) hí kě gbé
give chief dog (102) (S)VDO

- (106) hĩ gbé kē
give dog chief
'Give the dog to the chief.' (102) (S)VOD
- (107) hĩ nε kē
give it chief
'Give it to the chief.' (102) (S)VOD
- (108) hĩ nɔ bla
give him rice
'Give him rice.' (102) (S)VDO
- (109) hĩ Do Nyema
give Do Nyema
'Give Nyema to Do.' (102) (S)VDO

ITALIAN

- (110) M. offre il fiore a G.
'M. offers the flower to G.' (informant) SVOD
- (111) M. offre a G. il fiore
M. offers to G. the flower
'M. offers the flower to G.' (informant) SVDO
- (112) M. glielo offre
M. to-him-it offers
'M. offers it to him.' (informant) SDOV
- (113) M. lo offre a lui
M. it offers to him
'M. offers it to him.' (informant) SOVD
- (114) M. lo offre a G.
M. it offers to G.
'M. offers it to G.' (informant) SOVD
- (115) M. offre a lui il fiore
M. offers to him the flower
'M. offers him the flower.' (informant) SVDO
- (116) M. offre il fiore a lui
M. offers the flower to him
'M. offers him the flower.' (informant) SVOD

JAMAICAN CREOLE

- (117) Jan shuo Kieti di plom
'John showed Katie the plum.' (81) SVDO

- (118) Jan shuo di plom tu Kieti
'John showed the plum to Katie.' (81) SVOD

LITHUANIAN

- (119) Tėvas dāvė vaikui óbuolį
father gave child apple
'Father gave the child an apple.' (157) SVDO
- (120) Jis mán dovanójo knýga
he me gave book
'He gave me a book (as a gift).' (158) SVOD
- (121) Jis mán niėko nėdavė
he me nothing not-gave
'He didn't give me anything.' SDOV

SWAHILI

- (122) Ni-na-toa kalamu kwa kaka yangu
I-pres. -give pencil loc. brother my
'I give a pencil to my brother.' (Loogman, 329) SVOD
- (123) Ni-na-toa kaka yangu kalamu
I-pres. -give brother my pencil
'I give my brother a pencil.' (informant) SVDO
- (124) Ni-ta-m-pa kaka yangu kalamu
I-fut. -him-give brother my pencil
'I will give my brother a pencil.' (Loogman, 330) SVDO
- (125) Ni-ta-m-pa kalamu kaka yangu
I-fut. -him-give pencil brother my
'I will give my brother a pencil.' (informant) SVOD
- (126) A-me-m-jengea baba yake nyumba
he-perf. -him-build for father his house
'He has built a house for his father.' (Loogman, 330) SVDO

SWEDISH

- (127) han gav boken at flickan
he gave book the to girl the
'He gave the book to the girl.' (85) SVOD
- (128) han gav flickan boken
he gave girl the book the
'He gave the book to the girl.' (85) SVDO

- (129) han gav henne boken
 he gave her book the
 'He gave her the book.' (85) SVDO

YIDDISH

- (130) mir gibn es dem kind
 we give it to the child
 'We give it to the child.' (324) SVOD
- (131) mir shikn der bobe gelt
 we send to the grandmother money
 'We send the grandmother money.' (324) SVDO

SOV Languages -- Variable Order

KAPAU

- (132) apaka gaiyank*oi hope'a quwi'i
 woman husband kaukau give
 'The woman is giving her husband kaukau.' (47) SDOV

TELEFOL

- (133) níyó kaábák mâk tanúm beémí koób'mí
 I an axe the man I-gave-to-him
 'I gave the man an axe.' (13) SODV
- (134) oókén úta mán kafal'éebo
 her mother child she-is-showing-it-to-her
 'Her mother is showing it to her.' (13) SD(O)V

TURKISH

- (135) mektubu Ali? ye gösterdim
 letter to-Ali I showed
 'I showed the letter to Ali.' (36) (S)ODV
- (136) cocuğa hikâyeyi anlatti
 to-the-child the-story she-told
 'She told the child the story.' (240) (S)DOV
- (137) hikâyeyi bir çocuğa anlatti
 the-story a-to-child she-told
 'She told a story to the child.' (240) (S)ODV
- (138) hizmetçi-ye bir palto vereceğiz
 to-the-servant a coat we-are-going-to-give
 'We are going to give the servant a coat.' (36) (S)DOV

VSO Languages -- Variable Order

- (139) kwo?² hna?² xuih²¹² ?mo?² síh¹²
give I child chair
'I'm giving the child a chair.' (113)

OAXACA CHONTAL

- (140) Kán'esper itewxá liñekwé?
(she) left-for-(him) his-dinner (for) her-lover
'She left her lover his dinner.' (24)
- (141) móygi móygi kán'esper liñekwe itewxá?
morrow tomorrow (she) left-for-(him) (for) her-lover his-dinner
'Every day she left her lover his dinner.' (25) V(S)DO
- (142) kúpa elmel^yu páypa liw'á
(He) gave the-money (he) gave-(it)-to his-son
'He gave the money to his son.' (25) V(S)O + V(S)D

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